

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF PUNARNAVA-CAFFEINE HYDROGEL EYE PATCH FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF PERIORBITAL PUFFINESS AND DARK CIRCLE

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates The formulation and evaluation of an herbal hydrogel eye patch designed to manage periorbital puffiness and dark circles. The formulation utilizes a polymeric base to provide sufficient adhesion, hydration, and controlled release of active herbal constituents. The periorbital region is particularly sensitive and susceptible to fatigue-related symptoms, including swelling and pigmentation, primarily resulting from poor microcirculation, fluid retention, and decreased skin elasticity. punarnava (*Boerhavia diffusa*) and Caffeine were selected as active ingredients. punarnava demonstrates anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and mild diuretic properties, which may contribute to reducing under-eye swelling and fluid accumulation. caffeine promotes microcirculation and aids in minimizing dark circles by decreasing vascular congestion in the periorbital area. The hydrogel base provided sustained hydration, a cooling effect, and improved skin contact time, thereby enhancing the delivery

of active components. the prepared formulations were evaluated for appearance, flexibility, pH, adhesion, hydration ability, and skin compatibility. The results indicated that the hydrogel eye patches were stable, non-irritant, and suitable for application on sensitive under-eye skin.

Overall, the study suggests that the developed herbal hydrogel eye patch is a safe, effective, and convenient cosmetic approach for improving periorbital appearance.”

KEYWORDS: Herbal hydrogel eye patch, Punarnava, Caffeine, Periorbital Puffiness, Dark circles, Skin-friendly, Natural cosmetics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cosmeceutical Management of Periorbital Puffiness and Dark Circle:

1.1 Periorbital Area^[1,2,3]

- The periorbital area surrounds the eye socket and includes the upper/lower eyelids, inner and outer can thus, infra-orbital area, and tear trough.
- Protects the eyes and facilitates eyelid movement.
- Skin is thin, delicate, and highly prone to fatigue, swelling, pigmentation, and other cosmetic concerns.
- Sparse collagen and elastin fiber reduce elasticity and strength.
- Minimal subcutaneous fat exposes underlying blood vessels and muscles.
- Few or absent sebaceous glands cause dryness.
- Rich network of superficial blood vessels contributes to vascular pigmentation like dark circles.

1.2 Periorbital Puffiness^[15]

- **Bags under the eyes are persistent bulges or swellings beneath the lower eyelids resulting from structural changes in the periorbital tissues.** These changes involve fat prolapse, fluid accumulation, or weakening of connective and muscular support.
- Multiple factors contribute to under-eye bags, **including ageing, genetics, fluid retention, lack of sleep, allergies and sinus issues, lifestyle factors, and medical conditions.** Each is defined below, along with associated prevention strategies and diagnostic considerations.

How to Prevent Bags Under the Eyes?

- Maintaining a regular sleep routine.
- Stress-reduction practices such as meditation or controlled breathing.
- Hydration.

1.3. Periorbital Hyperpigmentation(Darck Circles)^[2,3,4]

- Periorbital hyperpigmentation (POH), commonly known as **dark circles**, is a frequent dermatological condition.
- It presents as **bilateral brown, dark brown, or blackish discoloration** around the eyes.
- It is an **aesthetic concern** that makes the face appear tired, stressed, or aged.
- POH can affect individuals of **all ages and skin types**, but is more common in young adults and females.
- It is a **multifactorial condition**, involving pigmentation, vascular factors, structural changes, and lifestyle factors.

Major causes include

- Excess melanin deposition (pigmentary type)
- Visible blood vessels (vascular type)
- Skin laxity and tear trough shadowing (structural type).

Genetic predisposition, stress, lack of sleep, and environmental factors are also commonly associated risk factors.

POH significantly affects **quality of life and psychological well-being** due to cosmetic concern.

1.4. Hydrogel Eye Patch^[5]

Hydrogels are three-dimensional polymers that are cross linked and contain hydrophilic groups that allow them to hold onto water without disintegrating. Polymers can be used to create hydrogels. Water fills the gaps between the macromolecules, causing the complex to swell and become a hydrogel. Due to the hydrophilic functional groups in the polymers, which hydrate in presence of aqueous conditions, the hydrogel have the capacity to absorb water. The hydrogel can't dissolve in water because of the crosslinks in the polymer network chains. Depending on their origin, polymer content, biodegradability, and arrangement, hydrogels come in various forms. Hydrogels vary in type based on their source, polymer composition, biodegradability, and structure. They can be classified by their crosslinking type, physical appearance, the electrical charge of their network and the method of preparation.^[1] Hydrogels exhibit great potential in the management of dark circles, wrinkles, fine lines, and puffiness—all of which are prevalent in the majority of the world's aging population. They can also be used in cosmetic under-eye procedures. Hydrating the sensitive area beneath your eyes is the primary goal of hydrogel under eye patches.

Fig.no 1.1: Hydrogel Eye Patch.

Characteristics

- **Moisturizing:** Delivers intense hydration to the eye area.
- **Cooling/Soothing:** Often provides a cooling or soothing effect.
- **Thin and flexible:** Conforms to the contours of the eye area
- **Non-irritating:** Generally gentle on sensitive skin.
- **Targeted delivery:** Can be infused with specific ingredients for eye concerns.

Advantages

- **Hydrate & Plump:** Intense moisture for the delicate eye area.
- **Reduce Puffiness:** Cooling effect reduces swelling.
- **Smooth Fine Lines:** hydrating effects soften those pesky lines.
- **Easy Peasy:** Mess-free and super convenient.
- **Targeted TLC:** Formulated with specific ingredients for dark circles, wrinkles, etc.
- **Soothing Bliss:** Perfect for sensitive skin or post-workout relaxation.

Applications

- Applied to the periorbital (under-eye) area.
- Used to reduce puffiness and under-eye swelling.
- Helps in lightening dark circles.
- Provides intense hydration to under-eye skin.

2. PLANT PROFILE

2.1 *Boerhavia diffusa*^[7]

- Botanical name-. *Boerhavia diffusa*
- Family-Nyctaginaceae
- Division-Magnoliopsida
- Class- Magnoliopsida
- Order-Caryophyllales
- Genus- *Boerhavia*
- Species- *Diffusa, hirsute*
- Part used -Roots
- Habitat- India, China, America, Islands, Africa.
- Common Name- Punarnava (Sanskrit), Hogweed (English), Gadha Purna (Hindi), Mukkurattai (Tamil)
- Chemical constituents: - Punarnavine (Alkaloids), β -sitosterol (Phytosterols), Liriodendrin (lignans), Punarnavoside (Rotenoids), Boerhavine (Xanthenes) and Potassium nitrate (Salts). The roots contain the rotenoids boeravinones AI, BI, C2, D, E and F, hydroxyl Serine, Sitosterol Oleate, Sitosterol Palmitate.

Fig no 2.1: - *Boerhavia diffusa*.

- Uses-
 1. Diuretic effect → edema reduction
 2. Anti-inflammatory action → swelling reduction
 3. Antioxidant activity → pigmentation & aging control
 4. Renal & hepatic protection
 5. Anti-angiogenic potential

2.2: - Caffeine

- Biological Source: Caffeine is a natural alkaloid obtained mainly from the dried leaves or seeds of plants such as *Camellia sinensis* (Tea) and *Coffea arabica* (Coffee).
- Family: Theaceae (Tea)
- Geographical Source: Widely cultivated in India, China, Sri Lanka, Brazil, and other tropical and subtropical regions.
- Chemical Constituents: caffeine, tea and coffee plants contain polyphenols, tannins, flavonoids, and antioxidants, 1,3,7-Trimethylxanthine
Major constituent: Caffeine (methylxanthine alkaloid)

- Uses:
 1. Vasoconstrictive action: Reduces dilation of blood vessels and minimizes
 2. Antioxidant activity: Protects skin from oxidative stress and free radical damage.
 3. Anti-inflammatory activity: Helps reduce inflammation around the eye area.
 4. Reduces puffiness and edema: Promotes microcirculation and fluid drainage.
 5. Improves blood circulation: Enhances appearance of tired-looking eyes.
 6. Skin rejuvenation: Commonly used in eye creams, gels, and hydrogel eye patches.

3. MATERIAL AND METHOD

Table No 3.1: List of ingredients and their sources.

Sr.no.	Chemicals	Sources
1	Punarnava root extract	Lab prepared
2	Caffeine	Lab prepared
3	Carbopol 940	CDH Fine Chemicals
4	Propyleneglycol	Loba chemie pvt. ltd Mumbai
5	Glycerin	Loba chemie pvt. ltd Mumbai
6	Honey	Organic food suppliers
7	Aloe vera gel	Lab prepared
8	Triethanolamine	S. D. Fine-Chem Ltd, Mumbai
9	Purified water	Laboratory

Table no 3.2: List of Equipment's.

Sr.no.	Name of Equipment'
1	Soxhlet Apparatus
2	Hot plate
3	Beaker, test tube,
4	Molds
5	Measuring cylinder
6	Stirrer, porcelain dish

METHODOLOGY OF ISOLATION

Procedure: -25gm of Punarnava root powder was placed into the thimble and placed in the Soxhlet chamber. 200 ml of selected solvent (ethanol) were placed in a round bottom flask and assembled for Soxhlet extractor then the distillation process was begun. After completed the extraction process, the solvent and extractor were placed on water bath to evaporate the solvent.^[15]

Table no 3.3: -Extraction of Punarnava root extract.

Soxhlet extraction	Extraction of punarnava

Procedure: -20gm of Tea leaves powder was placed into the round bottom flask 250 ml of selected solvent (water) were placed in that, then the distillation process was begun in reflux condenser. After completion of the extraction process, the solvent and extractor were filtered then placed on water bath to evaporate the solvent.^[15]

Table no 3.4: -Extraction of caffeine.

Soxhlet extraction	Extraction of caffeine

PREPARATION OF HERBAL EYE PATCH^[8,9]**1. Preparation of polymer solution**

- To prepare polymer solution, accurately weigh Carbopol 940 was dispersed in purified water allowed to hydrate to form the gel base and keep it separately.

2. Preparation of extract mixture

- Dissolve the required amount of **glycerin** in purified water.
- Add **Punarnava extract, caffeine extract, honey, and Aloe vera gel** with continuous stirring until a homogeneous mixture is obtained.

3. Mixing of two phases

- The extract mixture is added directly to the polymer solution employed with frequent stirring for 2 minutes. And The extract mixture is added directly to the polymer solution employed with frequent stirring the resulting mixture was poured into eye patch moulds.
- The filled mold were then left to cool at room temperature for five minutes, allowing the hydrogel to set or 2 minutes.
- Once solidified, the under-eye patches were carefully removed from the molds (demolded). and the final product was stored in a well-closed container to maintain its integrity and prevent degradation.

Table no 3.3: -Formulation of Herbal Hydrogel eye patch.

Sr.no	Ingredients	F1
1	Punarnava root extract	1.5g
2	Caffeine	0.5g
3	Carbopol 940	1g
4	Propylene glycol	8g
5	Glycerin	3ml
6	Honey	0.5ml
7	Alovera gel	5g
8	Triethanolamine	q.s
9	Purified water	q.s

Fig no 3.1: Hydrogel Eye Patch.

4. PREFORMULATION STUDIES

PHYSICOCHEMICAL PARAMETERS -*Boerhaavia diffusa* Linn. root powder.

Table no 4.1: - Foreign matter test.

Sr.no.	Name of Ingredients	Observation	Inference
1	Punarnava root powder		No foreign matters are found
2	Caffeine		No foreign matters are found

DETERMINATION OF LOSS ON DRYING (LOD) AND

DETERMINATION OF TOTAL ASH VALUE

Table No. 4.2:- Determination of

Initial weight=34.910gm	Weight of empty dish (x) = 30.804 gm
Weigh of sample after 1 st drying = 34.740gm	Weight of dry powder taken (y) = 2.004 gm
Weight of sample after 2 nd drying =34.734 gm	Weight of dish + ash (z) = 31.080 gm
Difference between both drying=0.176gm	Weight of ash = 0.276 gm
Percentage yield =0.50 %	Total ash value = 13.77%

loss on drying (lod) and Total ash value

DETERMINATION OF ACID INSOLUBLE ASH VALUE

DETERMINATION OF ACID WATER SOLUBLE ASH VALUE

Table No. 4.3:- Determination of acid in-soluble ash value and water soluble ash value.

Sample weight $w_s = 2$ gm	Sample weight = 2.004 g
Crucible weight $w = 30.804$ gm	Empty dish = 30.804 g
Crucible weight+ ash weight $w^f = 30.882$ gm	Water insoluble ash dish + residue = 31.069
Acid insoluble ash =3.9%	% Water Soluble Ash Value = 0.55%

PRELIMINARY PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING ^[9,11]

TESTS FOR GLYCOSIDES

1. Tests for Cardiac Glycosides

a) Baljeet's test

A section shows yellow to orange colours with sodium picrate.

b) Liebermann's test (for bufadienolides)

Add 2 ml plant extract to 2 ml acetic anhydride, cool in ice, add H_2SO_4 carefully along test tube sides. Colour change from violet to blue-green indicates steroid nucleus.

2. Tests for Anthraquinone Glycosides

a) Borntrager's test: To 3 ml extract, add dilute H_2SO_4 , boil, and filter.

Add equal volume benzene or chloroform, shake, separate organic layer, add ammonia.

Ammoniacal layer turns pink or red.

3. Tests for Saponin Glycosides

Foam test: Shake drug extract or dry powder vigorously with water. Persistent stable foam observed.

4. Tests for Cyanogenetic Glycosides: Add 3% aqueous mercuric nitrate solution to dry drug powder or extract. Metallic mercury forms.

TESTS FOR TANNINS AND PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS

To 2–3 ml of aqueous or alcoholic extract, add few drops of the following:

a) 5% $FeCl_3$ solution: Deep blue-black colour.

b) Lead acetate solution: White ppt.

TESTS FOR ALKALOIDS

Evaporate extracts (aqueous, alcoholic, chloroform) separately. Add dilute HCl, shake, filter, and perform:

- a) **Dragendorff's test:** Add a few drops of Dragendorff's reagent to filtrate. Orange-brown ppt. formed.
- b) **Mayer's test:** Add a few drops of Mayer's reagent to filtrate. Cream or white ppt. formed.

TEST FOR FLAVONOIDS

(a) **Shinoda test:** To dry powder of extract, add 5ml 95% ethanol, few drops conc. HCL and 0.5g magnesium turnings. Orange, pink, red to purple colour appears.

(b) **Sulphuric acid test:** On addition of sulphuric acid Flavones and flavone dissolve into it. deep yellow colour appears.

TEST FOR STEROIDS

(a) **Salkowski reaction:** To 2ml of extract, add 2ml chloroform and add 2ml con.H₂SO₄ Shake well. Chloroform layer appears red and acid layer shows greenish yellow fluorescence.

(b) **Liebermann-Burchard reaction:** Mix 2ml extract with chloroform. Add 1-2 ml acetic anhydride and 2 drop cons. H₂SO₄ from the side of test tube. First red then blue and finally green colour appears.

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING OF ETHANOLIC EXTRACT

Sr.no.	Test	Inference	
		PUNARNAVA	ROOT EXTRACT
TESTS FOR CARDIAC GLYCOSIDES			
1	Baljeet's Test:	-ve	
2	Liebermann's Test (for bufadienolides)	-ve	
TESTS FOR ANTHRAQUINONE GLYCOSIDES			

1	Borntrager's Test	-ve	
TEST FOR CYANOGENETIC GLYCOSIDE			
1	Sodium Picrate Test	-ve	
TESTS FOR TANNINS AND PHENOLIC COMPOUND			
1	Lead Acetate Solution	+ve	
TESTS FOR ALKALOIDS			
1	Dragendorff's test	+ve	
2	Mayer's test	+ve	
TEST FOR STEROIDS			
1	Salkowski reaction	+ve	
2	Liebermann-Burchard reaction	+ve	
TEST FOR FLAVONOIDS:			
1	Shinoda test	+ve	
2	Sulphuric acid test	+ve	

5. EVALUATION PARAMETER

- 1. PHYSICAL PARAMETERS:** The colour and odour of the prepared herbal bath bomb were observed with naked eye keeping it on white background. The odour of the bath bomb was smelled.^[12]

2. **pH:** The pH of bath bomb was determined by using digital pH meter. Take 1 gm of powder and dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water and take apart for two hours. Then measurement of pli of formulation was done by dipping the glass electrode completely into the solution three times and the average values are reported. ^[12]
3. **SKIN IRRITATION TEST:** -Apply the bath bomb paste sample at the wrist of the human volunteer. Mark the reason with black marker. Observe for at least 1 hours. Note in case any reaction occurred. ^[2]
4. **THICKNESS OF PATCHES:-** Thickness of each patch were measured of respective polymer by thickness gauge. The thickness of a transdermal patch is measured using a micrometer or vernier caliper. The patch is checked at 3–5 different points to ensure uniformity. All readings are recorded and the average thickness is calculated. This helps confirm uniform drug distribution and consistent drug release.
5. **MOISTURE CONTENT:** Films were kept in desiccators at temperature for 24 hrs. After 24 hrs. the films are to be reweighed and determined the percentage moisture uptake from the mentioned %Moisture uptake = $(\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight} \times 100) / \text{Initial weight}$.
6. **FOLDING ENDURANCE:** folding endurance were found by folding the respective patches of respective polymers up to 100 times or more than 100 times.
7. **WEIGHT UNIFORMITY:** The average weight and standard deviation values were calculated from the individual weight.
8. **SWELLING INDEX:** The hydrogel patch is cut into uniform size and weighed (W_0), then immersed in water or buffer for a fixed time. After removal, excess liquid is blotted and the swollen patch is reweighed (W_t) to calculate the swelling index.
9. **DETERMINATION OF STABILITY:** Store the hydrogel eye patch at room temperature and refrigeration. Observe at regular intervals (e.g., weekly) for changes in color, texture, odor, and note any phase separation, rancidity, or hardening. Record observations to decide the shelf life and stability of the hydrogel eye patch.

6. RESULT

1) PHYSICAL PARAMETER

Table no 6.1: - Physical parameter.

Sr. no.	Tests	Formulations
		F1
1	Color	Pale yellow
2	Clarity	Transparent
3	Texture	Smooth

Fig no.6.1 Physical evaluation.

1) pH DETERMINATION

Table no 6.2: - Determination pH.

Parameters	F1
pH	5.86

Fig no6.2: – Determination of pH.

2) SKIN IRRITATION TEST

Table no 6.3: -skin irritation.

Parameters	F1
Time	1 hour
Interpretation	No irritation

Fig.no.6.3:- skin irritation test

3) THICKNESS OF PATCH

Table no. 6.4:- Thickness of patch.

	0.49mm
Fig no. 6.4:- Thickness of patch	

4)	MOISTURE CONTENT	0.25%
5)	FOLDING ENDURANCE	115
6)	WEIGHT UNIFORMITY	2.03mg

8) DETERMINATION SWELLING INDEX

Table no. 6.5:- determination of swelling index.

	31%
Fig no. 6.5:- determination of swelling index.	

9) DETERMINATION OF STABILITY

Table no. 6.6:- determination of stability.

Condition	F1
Room Temperature	No Change
Refrigerator	No Change
Elevated Temperature	No Change

EVALUATION OF RESULTS OF HERBAL HYDROGEL EYE PATCH**Table no 6.7. - Evaluation parameters of Herbal Hydrogel Eye Patch.**

Sr.no.	Parameters	F1
1	Colour	Pale yellow
2	Clarity	Transparent
3	Texture	Smooth
4	Ph	5.86
5	Skin Irritation	Non irritant
6	Stability test	No Change

7) CONCLUSION

The present study was aimed to design and evaluate Herbal Hydrogel Eye Patch using *Boerhavia diffusa* (Punarnava root extract) and caffeine. The formulation was successfully prepared and evaluated for various physicochemical and performance parameters.

All formulations exhibited satisfactory physical characteristics such as acceptable color variation, pleasant odor, solid state, uniform flat-round shape, and suitable texture, indicating successful formulation development. In this generation, the increase in screen time may cause an increase in the under eye darkness, puffiness and inflammation. To tackle this problem, we have introduced a formulation mainly using herbal ingredients.

The evaluation studies demonstrated that the prepared Eye Patch showed desirable clarity. pH of all formulations was found to be within a skin-friendly range, confirming their suitability for topical application.

Skin irritation studies revealed no signs of irritation or adverse reactions, indicating that the formulations are safe and compatible with skin. In the incorporation of natural herbal ingredients like using *Boerhavia diffusa* (Punarnava root extract) and caffeine. These are rich in antioxidants and skin-beneficial properties. This approach not only enhances the therapeutic and cosmetic value of the product but also promotes the use of eco-friendly and chemical-free alternatives in personal care.

Thus, it can be concluded that herbal patch formulated using these natural ingredients can be successfully developed with good stability, safety, and effectiveness, offering a promising and sustainable alternative to conventional eye products.

8 REFERENCE

1. Shikha Mishra, Vidhu Aeri, Praveen Kumar Gaur, Sanjay M. Jachak. Phytochemical, Therapeutic, and Ethnopharmacological Overview for a Traditionally Important Herb: *Boerhavia diffusa* Linn. *Phytomedicine / BioMed Research International*. 2014.
2. Sarkar R, Ranjan R, et al. *Periorbital Hyperpigmentation: A Comprehensive Review*. Journal of Clinical and Aesthetic Dermatology. 2016. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC4756872/>
3. Roberts WE. *Periorbital hyperpigmentation: review of etiology, medical evaluation, and aesthetic treatment*. J. Drugs Dermatol., 2014.
4. Michelle L, et al. *Treatments of Periorbital Hyperpigmentation: A Systematic Review*. Dermatologic Surgery. 2021. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32740208/>
5. <https://www.ijpsjournal.com/article/Revitalizing-Under-Eye-Hydrogel-Patches-Development-and-Assessment>.
6. Dinesh Kumar R, Lakshmanan G, Kalpana R, Senthilkumar S, Rajan M. Protective role of *Boerhavia diffusa* root extract in methotrexate-induced renal injury: evidence from oxidative stress, molecular, and immunohistochemical markers. *BMC Complementary Medicine and Therapies*. 2026; Article 53 (or article number as per journal).
7. Verma P, Lal VK. Punarnava – A Natural Remedy by Ayurveda. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2014; 6(8): 1–6.
8. Divya R, Ansary PY, Oommen SM, Shincymol VV. A review on Punarnava (*Boerhaavia diffusa* Linn.). *Int. J. AYUSH.*, 2023; 12(6).
9. Telang S, Ahmad I, Shirao A, Shenmare V, Rewatkar S. Formulation and evaluation of herbal eye patches for under-eye hydration and dark circle reduction. *Int. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025; 3(5): 1810-1819.
10. Verma P, Lal VK. *Punarnava – A natural remedy by Ayurveda*. *International Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2014; 6(8): 1–6.
11. Divya Raj, P. Y. Ansary, Sara Moncy Oommen, & Shincy Mol V. V. **Phytochemical evaluation of root of Punarnava (*Boerhaavia diffusa* Linn.)**. *Kerala Journal of Ayurveda*, 2024; 3(1).
12. Riya Z. S. et al. “Evaluation of herbal hydrogel under eye patch.” *Department of Pharmaceutics, The Dale View College of Pharmacy and Research Centre, Punalal, TVM, Kerala, India*.

13. Robinson R, Sharma MP, Vikash SR, Sasthiri K. *Extraction of Caffeine from Coffee and Tea*. Design Project Report (CHB441), Department of Chemical Engineering, Hindustan Institute of Technology and Science, Chennai, India; April 2022.
14. Cleveland Clinic. Bags under the eyes: Causes, treatments, & prevention tips [Internet]. Cleveland Clinic; [cited 2026 Jun 3].
15. Khedkar SV, Aher R. Cosmetic Hydrogel Under Eye Patch: Review. *International Journal for Research Trends and Innovation (IJRTI)*. 2022; 7(8): 1621-1636. ISSN: 2456-3315.
16. Ashihara H, Crozier A. Caffeine: a well-known but little mentioned compound in plant science. *Trends Plant Sci.*, 2001; 6(9): 407-413.
17. Herman A, Herman AP. Caffeine's mechanisms of action and its cosmetic use. *Skin Pharmacol. Physiol.*, 2013; 26(1): 8-14.